

Real-Time Bidirectional ASL Alphabet Recognition Using Hand Landmarks and a BiLSTM–Attention Network with Confidence-Gated Decoding

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Abstract

We present a real-time American Sign Language (ASL) fingerspelling system for recognizing the static alphabet (A–Z) from webcam video and rendering typed text back into sign exemplars. For sign-to-text, we extract 21 hand landmarks per frame using MediaPipe Hands (63-D (x, y, z) features) and classify 30-frame landmark sequences using a stacked bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM) with a temporal attention mechanism. To stabilize real-time decoding, predictions are committed only when the top-class probability exceeds 0.9 and the same class persists for 12 frames. To prevent temporal overlap leakage, recordings are split in a *session-disjoint* manner before sliding window sequence generation. All results in this paper are based on a single signer and therefore reflect generalization to unseen recording sessions of the same signer (not cross-signer generalization). On a 26-class dataset of 2520 sequences (train/val: 1977/543), the model achieves 90.42% validation accuracy with Top-3 accuracy 97.42%. Runtime performance is benchmarked on Apple M3 (Metal), 16 GB RAM at 17.3 FPS for the full pipeline with mean end-to-end latency 57.75 ms. Errors are concentrated in visually similar handshapes (e.g., S→E, T→N). We discuss limitations (dynamic motion for J/Z, single-hand assumption, and single-signer data) and directions for robust, mobile, and sentence-level sign understanding.

1 Introduction

Sign language recognition can reduce communication barriers by enabling accessible human–computer interaction and assistive translation tools. However, real-time performance under webcam conditions is challenging due to background clutter, lighting variation, occlusions, and inter-signer differences.

Most vision-only systems either (i) process raw RGB frames using CNNs (often expensive at runtime and sensitive to appearance shifts) or (ii) use pose/landmark estimation to compress input into structured coordinates. In this work, we adopt the landmark-based approach: MediaPipe Hands yields 21 hand landmarks per frame [2], and we model short temporal sequences via a BiLSTM–attention classifier. This design targets high accuracy and low latency on consumer hardware.

A common pitfall in sequence classification from video is temporal overlap leakage: if overlapping sliding windows from the same recording are randomly split across training and validation, near-duplicate

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content can inflate reported metrics. We explicitly avoid this by performing session-disjoint splitting before windowing.

Contributions.

- A landmark-only real-time ASL alphabet recognizer using a 3-layer BiLSTM with attention over 30-frame windows.
- A confidence- and consistency-gated decoding strategy (0.9 probability threshold and 12-frame persistence) that stabilizes interactive spelling.
- A bidirectional application: sign-to-text with a word builder HUD and text-to-sign rendering via exemplar lookup.
- Leakage-free evaluation using session-disjoint splitting before windowing, plus baseline comparisons to quantify the role of temporal modeling and attention.

2 Related Work

Earlier sign recognition explored wearable sensors and gloves, improving signal quality but limiting usability. Modern vision methods frequently use CNNs on hand images, achieving strong accuracy but often requiring large datasets and heavier compute.

Pose/landmark pipelines provide a practical middle ground. MediaPipe and its hand landmark model enable real-time hand tracking on commodity devices [1, 2]. Landmark-based gesture recognition has shown excellent accuracy with lightweight neural models [11]. For temporal modeling, LSTMs [3] and bidirectional RNNs [4] capture sequential context, while attention mechanisms [5] help focus on informative timesteps.

In ASL alphabet recognition, recent works also leverage MediaPipe landmarks and deep models; for instance, a YOLOv8 transfer-learning approach reports high recognition performance using Mediapipe-assisted processing [12]. Our work differs by operating directly on landmark sequences with a dedicated temporal model and a decoding strategy designed for interactive typing stability, and by reporting session-disjoint results to reflect generalization across recording sessions.

3 Methodology

3.1 System Overview

Figure 1 summarizes the full pipeline:

1. Webcam capture \rightarrow MediaPipe Hands \rightarrow 21 landmarks/frame (63-D).
2. Maintain a 30-frame rolling buffer (sequence shape 30×63).
3. BiLSTM-attention classifier outputs $p(\text{letter} \mid \text{sequence})$.
4. Commit a letter only when: (i) $\max p \geq 0.9$ and (ii) the argmax class persists for 12 frames.
5. Update the word builder HUD; text-to-sign renders exemplars for typed words.

Figure 1: System architecture. Webcam frames are converted to landmark sequences using MediaPipe Hands, classified by a BiLSTM–attention model, and decoded using confidence and temporal consistency gating. A word builder HUD supports editing, and a text-to-sign module renders letter exemplars.

3.2 Data Collection and Preprocessing

We collected raw video frames for each alphabet class (A–Z) using a custom data-collection script. Each recording session captured approximately 300 frames per class. From each frame, we extracted hand landmarks using MediaPipe in single-hand static-image mode with a minimum detection confidence of 0.6. MediaPipe returns 21 hand keypoints with 3D coordinates (x, y, z) , which we flatten into a 63-dimensional feature vector per frame.

To model temporal dynamics, we construct fixed-length sequences using a sliding window of 30 frames with a stride of 10 frames. Each sequence is represented as a 30×63 tensor.

Leakage-free split protocol (session-disjoint). Random splitting of sliding window sequences can leak near-duplicate temporal content across train/validation because adjacent windows overlap in frames. To prevent this, we split recordings in a session-disjoint manner before windowing: recording sessions are assigned group ids, groups are split into train/validation, and sliding windows are generated only within each split. This ensures that no frames (and no overlapping windows) from the same session appear in multiple splits.

Signer scope. The dataset used in this paper is collected from a single signer with multiple sessions; therefore, reported metrics reflect generalization across sessions of the same signer.

Dataset statistics:

- 26 classes (A–Z), sequence length 30, features 63.

Figure 2: Data processing flow: frame capture \rightarrow landmark extraction \rightarrow session-disjoint split \rightarrow sequence formation (30×63) \rightarrow dataset serialization.

- Total: 2520 sequences; train/val: 1977/543 (session-disjoint).
- Sessions: approximately 104 training sessions and 28 validation sessions (300-image chunks).

Note on J and Z: Although included as two of the 26 classes, these letters are modeled as static poses rather than their canonical motion trajectories.

3.3 Model Architecture

Input is a landmark sequence $X \in \mathbb{R}^{30 \times 63}$. The network uses:

- 3 stacked BiLSTM layers: $128 \rightarrow 160 \rightarrow 128$ units (tanh), with L2 regularization ($\lambda = 0.001$), dropout 0.4, and batch normalization.
- A temporal attention layer that produces a weighted pooling over the 30 timesteps.
- Dense head: $256 \rightarrow 128$ (ReLU, L2=0.001, dropout 0.5).
- Softmax output over 26 letters.
- All BiLSTMs use `return_sequences=True` so the full hidden sequence $H \in \mathbb{R}^{30 \times 256}$ is available to the attention module.
- Dropout is applied as explicit Dropout layers (0.4 between BiLSTMs; 0.5 after each dense layer), rather than LSTM-internal dropout.

3.4 Training

We train in TensorFlow/Keras [8, 9] with Adam [6] (lr 10^{-3} , clipnorm 1.0). We apply cosine annealing (10-epoch warmup, decay to 10^{-6} over 300 epochs) following warm-restart scheduling ideas [7]. We use class weights and EarlyStopping (patience 40 on validation accuracy) with ModelCheckpoint to save the best model.

Augmentation uses a custom generator:

- Gaussian noise ($\sigma = 0.02$)
- Time warping ($\sigma = 0.2$)
- Magnitude warping ($\sigma = 0.2$)

Time-series warping augmentation is supported by prior work in time-series augmentation [10].

3.5 Real-Time Decoding and UI

At runtime, the app loads the trained model and performs streaming inference with a HUD overlay showing FPS, confidence, and a text buffer. Users can insert spaces, delete letters, and clear the buffer. Predictions are committed only when (i) the maximum predicted probability exceeds 0.9 and (ii) the predicted class persists for 12 consecutive frames, reducing false commits from transient misclassifications.

4 Experimental Setup

4.1 Splits and Reproducibility

All reported results use a session-disjoint split to prevent temporal overlap leakage from sliding window sequence construction. Recording sessions are grouped by session id, split into train/validation groups, and sliding windows are generated only after this split. Since the dataset is collected from a single signer, this evaluation measures generalization to unseen sessions of the same signer.

Random seed is fixed to 42. Software versions: Python 3.12.12, TensorFlow 2.20.0, Keras 3.12.0, MediaPipe 0.10.30, and NumPy 1.26.4.

Hardware: Apple M3 (Metal), 16 GB RAM.

4.2 Metrics

We report accuracy, top-k accuracy (k=3), and validation loss under session-disjoint evaluation.

4.3 Baselines and Ablations

To quantify the contribution of each design choice, we compare against:

- Frame MLP: frame-level features with no temporal model.
- Simple LSTM: unidirectional LSTM without BiLSTM or attention.
- Reduced BiLSTM: BiLSTM stack without attention pooling.

Table 1 summarizes baseline performance under the session-disjoint split.

Model	Val Accuracy	Parameters	Notes
BiLSTM + Attention (ours)	90.42%	1,360,536	Full model
Reduced BiLSTM	90.06%	184,470	No attention
Simple LSTM	88.77%	71,642	No BiLSTM/Attn
Frame MLP	67.22%	526,938	No temporal

Table 1: Baseline comparison under session-disjoint splitting (split before windowing).

Component	Mean (ms)	P95 (ms)	FPS
MediaPipe hand detection	19.08	19.49	52.4
BiLSTM+Attention inference	36.83	40.69	27.2
Full pipeline	57.75	–	17.3

Table 2: Runtime benchmark of the recognition pipeline.

5 Results

5.1 Validation (session-disjoint; Single Signer)

On the session-disjoint validation set (unseen sessions from the same signer), we obtain:

- Accuracy: 90.42%
- Top-3 accuracy: 97.42%
- Validation loss: 0.8911

5.2 Runtime Performance

Benchmarked on Apple M3 using 200 iterations after 20 warmup runs. Measurements were taken using the same webcam capture settings as the runtime application (OpenCV capture configuration). Benchmarking at 640×480 resolution using OpenCV capture (display enabled).

Table 2 reports end-to-end latency and throughput on the benchmark setup.

5.3 Error Analysis

Errors are concentrated among visually similar handshapes where subtle thumb/finger placement differences are difficult under landmark noise and viewpoint variation (e.g., S→E, T→N). The confidence+consistency gate reduces the likelihood of transient misclassifications being committed in live usage.

6 Application: Real-Time HUD and Text-to-Sign Rendering

The runtime interface overlays the video feed with a HUD that displays FPS, predicted letter, confidence, and a running text buffer. Users can insert spaces, delete letters, and clear the buffer. The text-to-sign module displays exemplar sign images for letters in the typed word using local assets, enabling a bidirectional demonstration of spelling.

Figure 3: Normalized confusion matrix on the session-disjoint validation split.

7 Limitations and Future Work

Dynamic motion for J/Z: While included in the 26 classes, J and Z are treated as static poses; motion trajectories are not modeled.

Single-hand assumption: Two-hand signs and occlusions are not addressed.

Single-signer dataset: All reported results are based on a single signer; therefore metrics reflect within-signer session generalization, not cross-signer generalization.

Data diversity: Broader signer and environment diversity is needed for stronger real-world robustness.

Future directions include collecting multi-signer datasets, modeling dynamic gestures for J/Z, multi-hand handling, domain-robust training across lighting/backgrounds/skin tones, and deployment via quantization and mobile runtimes. Extending from alphabet recognition to word-level and sentence-level translation would require larger datasets and richer context modeling.

Figure 4: Training curves (loss/accuracy) for the training run used to report session-disjoint results.

8 Code, Data, and Asset Licensing

Code and evaluation: The training, session-disjoint splitting, and evaluation scripts are available from the authors upon reasonable request.

Data: The dataset is self-collected using a webcam capture script that records 300-image sessions per letter. Raw video/images are not included in the arXiv submission; session-id split files and evaluation scripts can be shared to support deterministic reproduction.

MediaPipe model asset: The MediaPipe hand landmarker model (`hand_landmarker.task`) is provided by Google MediaPipe under the Apache License 2.0.

Text-to-sign exemplars: Exemplar images used for the demo are local assets and are not distributed with the arXiv submission. If distributed publicly in the future, they should include explicit licensing and attribution.

9 Ethical Considerations

Landmark-based systems can still exhibit performance disparities if training data lacks diversity. For deployment, evaluation should cover diverse users and environments, and the UI should surface confidence and allow corrections (backspace/clear) to reduce user harm from incorrect outputs.

10 Conclusion

We introduced a real-time ASL alphabet recognition system based on MediaPipe hand landmarks and a BiLSTM-attention classifier, stabilized by confidence- and consistency-gated decoding. Under session-disjoint evaluation (split before windowing) on a single-signer dataset, the method achieves 90.42% validation accuracy and maintains interactive performance at 17.3 FPS on Apple M3. This provides a base for broader sign language understanding systems, with clear directions for improving robustness through multi-signer training and dynamic gesture modeling.

References

- [1] Camillo Lugaresi, Jiuqiang Tang, Hadon Nash, Chris McClanahan, Esha Uboweja, Michael Hays, Fan Zhang, Chuo-Ling Chang, Ming Guang Yong, Juhyun Lee, Wan-Teh Chang, Wei Hua, Manfred Georg, and Matthias Grundmann. MediaPipe: A Framework for Building Perception Pipelines. *arXiv:1906.08172*, 2019.
- [2] Fan Zhang, Valentin Bazarevsky, Andrey Vakunov, Andrei Tkachenka, George Sung, Chuo-Ling Chang, and Matthias Grundmann. MediaPipe Hands: On-device Real-time Hand Tracking. *arXiv:2006.10214*, 2020.
- [3] Sepp Hochreiter and Jürgen Schmidhuber. Long short-term memory. *Neural Computation*, 9(8):1735–1780, 1997.
- [4] Mike Schuster and Kuldip K. Paliwal. Bidirectional recurrent neural networks. *IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing*, 45(11):2673–2681, 1997.
- [5] Dzmitry Bahdanau, Kyunghyun Cho, and Yoshua Bengio. Neural machine translation by jointly learning to align and translate. *arXiv:1409.0473 (ICLR)*, 2015.
- [6] Diederik P. Kingma and Jimmy Ba. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. *arXiv:1412.6980 (ICLR)*, 2015.
- [7] Ilya Loshchilov and Frank Hutter. SGDR: stochastic gradient descent with warm restarts. *arXiv:1608.03983 (ICLR)*, 2017.
- [8] Martín Abadi et al. TensorFlow: Large-scale machine learning on heterogeneous distributed systems. *arXiv:1603.04467*, 2016.
- [9] François Chollet. Keras. <https://keras.io/>, 2015.
- [10] Brian Kenji Iwana and Seiichi Uchida. Time series data augmentation for neural networks by time warping with a discriminative teacher. *arXiv:2004.08780*, 2020.
- [11] César Osimani, Juan Jesús Ojeda-Castelo, and Jose A. Piedra-Fernandez. Point cloud deep learning solution for hand gesture recognition. *International Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Artificial Intelligence*, 8(4):78–87, 2023.
- [12] Bader Alsharif, Easa Alalwany, and Mohammad Ilyas. Transfer learning with YOLOv8 for real-time recognition system of American sign language alphabet. *Franklin Open*, 8:100165, 2024.